

VETERINARY SCIENCES

ORGANIZATION OF ANTI-EPIDEMIC MEASURES IN THE KENNEL "DOG, CAT"

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Abstract

Maintenance of dogs in the nursery is carried out in accordance with the established rules. The maintenance system has a favorable effect on the health of animals.

Keywords: Dog, cat, animal health, nursery.

Introduction. In the multi-faceted work of Veterinary Services, one of the leading places is occupied by the Prevention of infectious diseases of animals (infectious and invasive). Although losses from them now account for about 5-6% of the total level of losses caused by diseases, this type of pathology poses a serious potential threat to the animal husbandry of the Republic. Currently, there are practically no low-risk infectious diseases. Failure to pay attention to the prevention issues of each of them creates great difficulties for both individual farms and the state as a whole [1]. Features of the course of epizootic with close contact of animals are associated, on the one hand, with repeated transmission of the pathogen of the disease and an increase in its virulence, on the other-with the development of immunological resistance of animals and, as a result, with the chronic course of previously absent infections (for example, panleukopenia). As a result, vaccination carried out during remission of the disease with animal welfare does not give the desired result: intensive immunity is not formed, and any stressful situation provokes the appearance of clinical signs of the disease.

In such conditions, improving the nursery becomes a difficult task. The most correct recommendation is to eliminate it completely or reduce the number of animals and carry out therapeutic and preventive measures against those who remain the most valuable [2].

However, this option is not always suitable for animal owners. In this case, first of all, we recommend mandatory compliance with sanitary requirements, such as disinfection and quarantine, in nurseries, which, unfortunately, are ignored even by doctors who come to the facility for rehabilitation. The most important task of preventing infectious diseases of dogs and cats is to maintain zoohygienic conditions that meet the biological needs of animals. So, for keeping dogs and cats, you need to choose dry, calm, protected from the wind. Cages and cages should be light and spacious. Floors in cages are made of wood. The general walking area is covered with sand, the upper layer of which is updated annually [2].

To do this, firstly, limit the number of people who have access to the territory of the aviary; secondly, accumulate livestock only from healthy dogs exported

from areas favorable for Infectious Diseases; thirdly, keep newly imported dogs in quarantine in a Specially Designated cage for this purpose (to avoid contact with other animals), where they are monitored for three weeks; fourth, perform sanitary and anti-epizootic measures: disinfection (sterilization), disinsection (destruction of harmful insects and ticks), deratization (destruction of rodents) [1,2,3].

In this regard, the purpose of our work is to analyze the organization of anti-epidemic measures in the nursery "dog, cat".

The values put forward in the research papers:

- Analysis of the epizootological situation in the Kennel "Dog, cat";
- Analysis of the conditions of maintenance of animals in the Kennel "Dog, cat";
- Analysis of the complex of anti-epizootic measures in the "Dog, cat" nursery.

Materials and methods. This thesis was written in the period from 2020 to 2021 during the course of practical work in the nursery "Dog, cat" Astana vetservice", as well as at the Department of Veterinary sanitation of the Kazakh agrotechnical university named after S. Seifullin.

Epizootological data were discussed on the basis of the veterinary report of the institution and the test report for the diagnosis of animal diseases issued by the veterinary laboratory and issued in the form of a histogram [4,5,6].

Cases of dog maintenance were recorded in accordance with the internal rules of the institution, as well as on the basis of information accumulated at the beginning of the internship [8,9].

It is established that the basis of anti-epizootic measures is carried out in accordance with order 587 of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and information about them is processed in accordance with veterinary accounting and as a result of joint experimental work [10,11,12].

Results obtained. Analysis of the epizootological situation in the "dog cat" nursery currently, 225 dogs are kept in the nursery. There were no cats in the study. For the purpose of preliminary diagnosis of infectious diseases of dogs in the nursery, in accordance with the plan approved by the Veterinary Department,

laboratory tests are carried out to identify antibodies to brucellosis of carnivores, rabies and plague of carnivores.

As for the scale of studies for Infectious Diseases and the level of detection of positive results in 2021, 89 (39.5 %) of 225 dogs were subjected to laboratory tests for brucellosis, 15 heads (6.6 %) for rabies and 46 heads (20.4 %) for plague. According to the results of the study, rabies antibodies were detected in 13 (5.7%) heads and quarantine measures were carried out in the nursery. In the general laboratory, a dog's head with clinical signs is sent for Rabies Research, and a blood serum is sent to detect antibodies to brucellosis and plague [7,10,12].

Analysis of the conditions of maintenance of animals in the "Dog cat " nursery during the summer practice in the nursery" dog cat", special attention was paid to the conditions of dog care. Their general condition, growth, development, health and work largely depend on the conditions of keeping dogs.

Keeping dogs in a nursery includes a set of measures aimed at preventing diseases, ensuring normal physiological functions of the body and maintaining high productivity of the animal. Activities for keeping dogs in the nursery are carried out daily in accordance with zoohygienic requirements.

The complex of maintenance measures includes::

- placement and care of animals;
- maintaining a normal air environment in their habitats;
- maintenance of the premises and territory of the nursery.
- in the warm season, at least once a decade, the booths and aviaries are washed with hot water;
- in summer, at least once every 1-2 months, all premises of service dogs are disinfected with a 3% solution of creoline, Lysol or formalin.
- cleaning of Dogs is carried out daily before feeding, as well as in all cases of contamination in a special place;
- in the cold season, dogs are put on a straw bed, which is changed at least once a week.

The aviaries are located and equipped on a high, dry place. The main material from which the fence is built is wood.

The aviary has a common roof consisting of a cabin measuring 3x4 M and an area of 6-9 square meters (Fig.1), forming a block of fencing.

Along the aviary in front of the facade there is a road with a hard surface and a recess for draining water from the pedestrian path.

Figure 1. Aviary blocks in the nursery.

Analysis of the complex of antiepidemiological measures in the " dog cat " nursery. The order of a veterinary doctor to prevent and eliminate diseases of Dogs is mandatory for the dog breeding department. In order to prevent the occurrence and spread of infectious diseases of dogs, preventive disinfection of dog

accommodation facilities and adjacent territories is carried out twice a year (in spring and autumn), and if necessary, more often on the established sanitary days. Dogs entering the departments are subject to immediate clinical examination and individual quarantine maintenance within 21 days.

A-Introduction of the vaccine

B- follow up after vaccination.

Figure 2. The moment of introduction of the rabies vaccine during quarantine.

During quarantine maintenance: - it is forbidden to move dogs from one enclosure to another; - every day all quarantine dogs are subject to veterinary examination and thermometry; - if necessary, animals are vaccinated against plague and rabies.

Vaccination of dogs against plague and rabies is carried out according to the plan of Veterinary and sanitary measures.

Disinsection, deacarization of premises and territories is also carried out according to a certain plan and schedule. Insulators, places of detention of sick and suspected dogs are disinfected daily.

Preventive vaccination against particularly dangerous diseases of dogs in the aviary is carried out once a year. Disinsection, deacarization, deworming, disinfection, deratization, inspection of places of detention are carried out in the nursery once every 2 months. Monitoring of the sanitary condition of fences is carried out daily.

Summary. According to this work, in 2021, 89 (39.5 %) of 225 dogs were subjected to laboratory tests for brucellosis, 15 heads (6.6 %) for rabies and 46 heads (20.4 %) for plague. According to the results of the study, rabies antibodies were detected in 13 (5.7%) heads and quarantine measures were carried out in the nursery.

Maintenance of dogs in the nursery is carried out in accordance with the established rules. The maintenance system has a favorable effect on the health of animals.

Quarantine measures are carried out in accordance with the order of the minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated June 29, 2015 No. 7-1/587 on approval of Veterinary (veterinary and sanitary) rules. Quarantine and anti-epizootic measures are carried out by special veterinary doctors.

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